

Effect of Solar Dryer and Direct Open Sun Drying Methods on Drying Air Temperatures and Moisture Content of Fish Bayad (*Bagrus bayad*)

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Abstract

The study of drying air characteristics of fish flakes (*Bagrus bayad*) has been studied under solar drying and open direct sun drying methods at the Department of Food Processing Engineering, University of El Imam El Mhadi - Kosti, Sudan. During June- August, 2022 and June- August 2023. An indirect natural convective solar dryer consisting of a solar air heater with flat plate concentrator and drying chamber with air duct to connect drying chamber to the solar collector were used in the experiments. The objectives of the present study were to investigate the effect of solar dryer and open direct sun drying methods on the drying air temperatures and final moisture content of fish flakes. The results of the experiments revealed that, there were a significant effect of solar dryer in increasing temperatures of the drying air and reducing its relative humidity, so that its holding capacity to carry water from moist fish was increased which result in lowering final moisture content of fish flakes when compared to the other samples of the same fish dried with open-direct sun. The average heated air temperature was 50.22°C at noon, while the average ambient air temperature was 37.92°C at noon with the significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$). The average heated air RH% was decreased (22.84%) when compared with ambient and exhausted air RH% which was found to be 26.24% and 29.07% for ambient and exhausted air RH% respectively. with the significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$). Drying of fish began with an initial moisture contents of 383.87% (d.b.) for both solar and direct sun drying experiments and end with the final moisture content of 53.51% (d.b.) and 208.6% (d.b.) for solar dryer and direct sun drying respectively. The high moisture contents of fish dried with direct sun may result in spoilage and deteriorated the fish during the storage periods.

Keywords: *Solar dryer, Open-direct sun, Fish flakes, Drying air temperature, Moisture content.*

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Introduction

Fish contributes significantly to global employment and food production, making it a great food source. Fish and goods related to fishing provide around 17% of the animal protein consumed worldwide. (Hin, et al., 2024). Fish provides a good source of high quality protein and contains many vitamins and minerals; which is almost cheaper than any others type of meat and therefore available to large number of people (Fellows and Hamptom, 1992). Fish is the primary food source in rural areas since it is less expensive to farm than other kinds of animals for meat production. Large amounts of meat are lost annually as a result of improper handling during storage and preservation. This is because meat has a high moisture content, which causes microorganisms like insects and mites to thrive and expand at a very quick rate. Fish is one of those foods that spoils quickly in terms of both quantity and quality. (HA, E. et al., 2021). Fish solar drying is an alternative to traditional sun drying involves the use of solar; there has been a great deal of research on development of solar dryers as an improved method of drying fish. This has proven that, by achieving higher drying temperatures and lower humidity, solar dryer can increase drying rate and produce a lower moisture content of the final products with an improvement in fish quality compared to traditional sun drying techniques. Fish drying to optimum moisture content is one of the most important methods of preserving food throughout the world (Waterman, 1976 and Toledo, 1980). As reported by (Waterman, 1981) the water content of fresh white fish is about 80 percent, fatty fish water content is usually less because fat replacing some amount of water. When fish is dried to below 15 percent, mould ceases to grow. (Prabhu and Balachandran, 1982) explained that, the recommended moisture content of dried fish is between 15-10% (wet basis).

Sun drying is the most widely used method of food preservation in the world. It is a straightforward and affordable process. This method is popular, but it has a lot of disadvantages, such as weather dependence and contamination from insects, dust, dirt, and sand particles. Furthermore, it may take a while for everything to dry. (Elhesain, et al., 2023). Drying is one of the oldest methods of food preservation, but it's also a difficult food processing process because it makes the dried product's quality poor sometimes. To further improve food durability, drying is one of the most widely used methods. (Abdalla., et al., 2023) Due to the steady increase in fuels cost and their uncertain availability, considerable attention has been given to solar energy as an alternative or supplement to fuels for heating air and consequently utilizing it in drying process (Al-Amir, 1997). Solar heating system to dry the air is the cleanest fuel, which produce no pollution at all, and practically economical. Also, solar heating to dry food and others crops can improve the quality of the product, while reducing wasted product thus improving the quality of live. By using solar energy for air heating the cost of the fuel can be reduced considerably. (Radajewski *et al.*, 1987); UNIFEM, 1993. (Birewar, 1996), (Huffman et al. 1980) and (Tiwari, 2002) described the natural convection as the passive solar system. In this system, air is heated and circulated naturally by buoyancy forces. As reported by (Upadhyaya, 1985) this system has many advantages; it can be in areas where power is not available, it doesn't need any mechanical and has no moving parts. The maintenance cost will be almost negligible. This system would be of great importance for drying at lower temperature applications. It utilized solar energy as the source of heat. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to measure the effect of solar dryer and direct open-sun drying methods on the drying air characteristics of fish bayad (*Bagrus bayad*).

Materials and Methods

Equipment

Natural convective solar dryer was used for carrying out the drying experiments of fish flakes, Fig. 1, Data logger: of DL2e make, marketed by Delta-T Devices, Cambridge, England and to which thermocouples were connected for temperature measurements of the drying air. Hygrometer: A digital hygrometer of Testo GmbH type 6350, made in Germany was used for measuring relative humidity of the drying air. Sensitive balance: A digital sensitive balance of model Yass-620 with capacity of 620 g and accuracy of ± 0.01 g. Scale of Yamato make, made in Japan was used to determine the loss of weight in fish samples. Oven: An oven of Electro Helios make, was used for fish moisture content determination and it had a temperature range of 0 -200°C. Hand watch was used for measuring the time of drying.

Figure 1. Natural Convective Solar Drier

Methods

Drying experiments were carried out using a natural convective solar dryer. It was located at the Department of Food Processing Engineering, University of El Imam El Mhadi, Kosti, Sudan. The dryer was placed on the top of the roof of the building in order to get a maximum exposure to solar radiation. The dryer consists of three detachable components namely; solar collector (air heater), drying chamber and air duct Fig. 1.

Solar Drying Tests

The solar drying experiments were carried out during June-August 2022 and June-August 2023. Fish Bayad (*Bagrus bayad*) was bought from, Kosti local market. The fish was classified as class one in terms of quality. It had a highest filleting yield (47%) and with very low oil content (Suliman, 1996).

The Preparation of Fish for Drying

Head and tail of the fish were cut and removed using stainless steel knife. Then the fish were cut longitudinally and all internal parts of gut, liver, gall, bladder and fat were removed (fats become rancid easily and will spoil the dried meat). The split fish was washed in clean water with a slight amount of sodium chloride (500 grams/10 Liters of water). The objective of this practice is to remove blood spots and dirt. Then fish was put in clean tray for 10 minutes to drain out excess water. Fish was de-boned and cut into pieces of thin-layers (5cm × 4cm). The pieces of fish were salted with sodium chloride using salt concentration of about 8% (Fellows and Hamptum, 1992; Elobied, 2003). The salt was added to stop

any growth of bacteria before drying test to be commenced. 6 kg of the prepared fish were loaded into 3 trays as a thin-layer. According to (Ertekin *et al.*, 2004), thinly sliced products dried faster due to the reduced distance the moisture travels.

A represented sample from the fish lot was taken and wrapped with aluminum foil for initial moisture content determination.

The starting time of drying process was recorded using a hand watch. Initially at zero time the following measurements were recorded.

a) Temperature measurements: The temperatures of the drying air were measured at the following locations:

- Near the entrance of solar collector (ambient air temperature).
- At the entrance of the drying chamber (heated air temperature).
- At the top opening of the drying chamber (exhausted air temperature).

b) Relative humidity measurements: The relative humidity was measured at the following locations.

- Near the entrance of solar collector (ambient air relative humidity).
- At the entrance of the drying chamber (heated air relative humidity).
- At the top opening of the drying chamber (exhausted air relative humidity).

The above-mentioned measurements were recorded at intervals of one hour throughout the experimental period, which took three days (33hr.) interrupted by two overnights. At the end of the drying period. A represented sample was taken and wrapped with aluminum foil for final moisture content determination using the oven method.

Sun Drying Test

This experiment was conducted for comparison between solar and open sun drying using fish flakes of bayad (*Bagrus bayad*). These experiments were done as a control to know the effects of solar dryer on the drying air temperature. A represented sample of two pieces of fish each 5cm × 4cm were taken from the same samples used for solar drying tests. These samples were put in a wire mesh tray and directly exposed to the sun radiation in an open area near the solar dryer. The starting time of the drying process was recorded using a hand watch. Initially at zero time the initial weight of these sample were recorded, then the lost in weights were recorded at interval of one hour throughout the experimental period, which took three days (33hr.) interrupted by two overnights. At the end of the third day the final weight of these samples was weighed using sensitive balance and the average was taken.

Moisture Content Determination

Initial and final moisture content were determined for both solar and direct sun drying according to the method described by (AOAC., 2005). In this method, duplicate samples of fresh and dried fish were used for initial and final moisture content, respectively. Two aluminum dishes were washed and put into the oven for about 3 hours to dry, and then the dishes were taken from the oven and placed into desiccators to cool to get their true weights. The aluminum dishes were weighed using a sensitive balance. To avoid loss or gain of moisture while weighing aluminum foil were used to wrap the samples. The weighed sample was placed into the oven, and the oven was set at 105°C for overnight. After that the samples were taken out and placed into the desiccators and left for about 20 minutes to cool. Then the samples were weighed using the sensitive balance. The moisture content of the samples was calculated using the following equations:

$$MC(w.b.) = \frac{W_w}{W_w + W_d} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$MC(d.b.) = \frac{W_w}{W_d} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where:

MC (w.b.) = fish moisture content on wet basis, percent

MC (d.b.) = fish moisture content on dry basis, percent

W_w = mass of water, g

W_d = mass of dry matter, g

Results and Discussions

Raising Heated Air Temperatures

Table 1. and Fig 2. Show the average ambient air, heated air and exhausted air temperatures plotted versus drying time of fish flakes during three consecutive days. It is clear that, the drying process is interrupted by two overnights. There is a remarkable difference between ambient air and heated air temperatures during the three days of the drying, this will be attributed to the fact that, when ambient air passes through the solar collector it is temperature was increased (i.e. air gain temperature from solar collector). The increase in heated air temperature at noon is remarkably greater than in the morning. This could be due to fact that at noon, the solar collector had absorbed sufficient heat to permit continuous heating of air. This result is in agreement with the finding of (Berinyuy, 2004) on his study of solar tunnel dryer of vegetables and other commodities in Cameroon. Statistical analysis using paired comparison t-test analysis (table 2), showed that, the difference between heated and ambient air temperatures is highly significant ($P \leq 0.05$). Also, in Fig. 2 it is clear that there is a difference between heated air and exhausted air (i.e. heated air after passing through moist fish in drying chamber), there is a decrease in exhausted air temperature, this because when heated air passes through moist fish there is a simultaneous heat and mass transfer between fish and drying air, so that the temperature of the air will decreased while its relative humidity was increased and the temperature of product (fish) will increased. For the three days of drying the difference between heated air and exhausted air temperatures starts to increase in morning, reaches a maximum value at noon and then decreases in evening. These results were in a good agreement with (Akoy, 2000) in his study of onion slices and (Ayoub, 2006) in her study of tomato slices.

Table 1. Average Temperatures of Ambient Air, Heated Air and Exhausted Air During the Three Days of the Experiments

Drying period		Ambient air temperature (°C)	Heated air temperature (°C)	Exhausted air temperature (°C)
Hours	Time			
0	8:30 a.m.	28.61	32.83	28.78
1	9:30	30.15	38.07	33.44
2	10:30	35.39	46.8	38.48
3	11:30	40.48	50.92	41.66
4	12:30 p.m.	40.31	51.12	42.61
5	1:30	40.44	51.33	42.33

6	2:30	41.92	50.48	44.42
7	3:30	42.22	50.32	46.54
8	4:30	40.77	49.28	45.65
9	5:30	39.19	44.37	42.76
10	6:30	37.12	40.11	39.08
Overnight	-		-	-
11	8:30 a.m.	27.78	32.36	29.1
12	9:30	30.19	40.47	32.56
13	10:30	34.18	45.68	37.95
14	11:30	35.91	47.48	40.67
15	12:30 p.m.	37.55	50.6	42.31
16	1:30	39.55	50.08	45.44
17	2:30	40.83	52.56	45.41
18	3:30	39.77	50.68	47.58
19	4:30	39.58	48.2	43.68
20	5:30	38.14	44.28	40.97
21	6:30	31.41	39.55	37.86
Overnight	-	-	-	-
22	8:30 a.m.	27.37	34.03	29.54
23	9:30	30.28	38.8	34.4
24	10:30	31.71	44.28	35.87
25	11:30	34.79	51.36	38.82
26	12:30 p.m.	35.91	49.96	41.3
27	1:30	37.8	50.72	43.51
28	2:30	39.77	51.28	44.41
29	3:30	39.41	50.2	46.54
30	4:30	39.73	49.88	43.8
31	5:30	38.73	46.76	41.2
32	6:30	36.31	41.91	38.3
Average	-	26.24	45.99	29.07

Statistical analysis using paired comparison t-test analysis (Table 2.) showed that the difference between heated and exhausted air temperatures is highly significant ($P \leq 0.05$)

Figure 2. Average Ambient, Heated and Exhausted Air Temperatures with Drying Time

Table 2. Statistical Analysis Using Paired Samples T-Test for Air Differences Between (a) - Heated Air and Ambient Air; (b) - Heated Air and Exhausted Air Temperatures

Pair	mean	N	Std. deviation	Std. error mean	correlation	Significant
Heated air	45.992	33	5.93063	1.0324	0.865	0.000
Ambient air	36.472	33	4.41381	0.7684		
Exhausted air	40.213	33	5.1830	0.9022	0.896	0.000

Lowering Heated Air Relative Humidity

Table 3 and Fig. 3 show the ambient air, heated air and exhausted air relative humidities plotted versus drying time for fish flakes drying during three consecutive days. Also, there are interruptions in the drying curves, which represent two overnights. There is a difference between ambient air and heated air relative humidity. Heated air relative humidity is lower than ambient air relative humidity. When the drying air heated by solar collector this result in lowering its relative humidity and raising its temperature and consequently the holding capacity to pull the water from the moist product was increased. Generally, all air relative humidities decreases to a maximum value at about noon and then increase towards evening period, this could be due to fact that at noon, the solar collector had absorbed sufficient heat to permit continuous heating of air so that its relative humidity was decreased. The average ambient air relative humidity is about 26.24%, while the average heated air relative humidity is about 22.84% and the difference between this two relative humidity are 3.40% (Table 3.). Statistical analysis using paired comparison t-test (table 4.) revealed that, the difference between heated and ambient air relative humidity is highly significant ($P \leq 0.05$). Also, in Fig. 3 it is clear that, for the three days of drying the difference between heated air and exhausted air relative humidity is great at the three mentioned time in the first day compared to those of second and third days. This could be due to fact that most of drying process takes place in the first day. Therefore, during the second and third days there is no moisture to be removed by heated air from fish flakes and consequently the difference between this two relative humidity was decreased.

Table 3. Relative Humidity of Ambient Air, Heated Air and Exhausted Air During the Three Days of the Experiments

Drying period		Ambient air relative humidity (%)	Heated air relative humidity (%)	Exhausted air relative humidity (%)
Hours	Time			
0	8:30 a.m.	41.85	38.65	43.05
1	9:30	37.15	34	40.9
2	10:30	30.7	26.3	38.65
3	11:30	24.1	21.5	31.6
4	12:30 p.m.	21.95	18.55	26.05
5	1:30	19.65	17.52	23.2
6	2:30	20.25	17.8	26.3
7	3:30	20.53	17.95	26.6
8	4:30	23.25	18.45	27.7
9	5:30	24.85	19.9	28.57
10	6:30	27.35	21.85	31.15
Overnight	-	=	-	-
11	8:30 a.m.	43.95	39.4	45.66
12	9:30	38.45	31.3	40.45
13	10:30	30.55	27.1	34.7
14	11:30	26.7	21.5	29.35
15	12:30 p.m.	21.65	17	24.55
16	1:30	19	16.65	22.15

17	2:30	18.6	15.9	20.25
18	3:30	19	15.85	20.5
19	4:30	19.7	17.4	21.95
20	5:30	20.5	17.75	21.75
21	6:30	23.4	20.75	23.9
Overnight	-	-	-	-
22	8:30 a.m.	44.05	41.94	45.35
23	9:30	36.3	32.4	38.4
24	10:30	30.3	23.1	23.6
25	11:30	23.55	21.06	27.85
26	12:30 p.m.	22.2	19.55	25.1
27	1:3	20.6	18.25	22.1
28	2:30	18.85	16.37	20.75
29	3:30	19.7	17.05	19.9
30	4:30	19.65	17.2	19.65
31	5:30	22.65	20.32	23.95
32	6:30	34.91	33.23	34.97
Average	-	26.24	22.84	29.07

Figure 3. Average Ambient, Heated and Exhausted Air Relative Humidities with Drying Time

Statistical analysis using paired comparison t-test (table 4) showed that the difference between heated and exhausted air relative humidities is highly significant ($P \leq 0.05$).

Table 4. Statistical Analysis Using Paired Samples T-Test for Relative Humidity Differences Between (a) - Heated Air and Ambient Air (b) - Heated Air and Exhausted Air

Pair	mean	N	Std. deviation	Std. error mean	correlation	Significant
Heated air	22.843	33	7.54335	1.3131	0.984	0.000
Ambient air	26.239	33	7.90230	1.3756		
Exhausted air	29.077	33	7.938	1.3877	0.945	0.000

The Solar Drying Kinetics of Fish Flakes

Fig. 4 shows the variation of moisture content with drying time for the three days of the drying. The drying rate is higher at the beginning of the drying process and decrease continuously with the advance of drying time. Also, it is clear that, there is no constant drying rate period in the drying of the fish flakes and all the drying process occurs during the falling rate period. The diffusion took place in the inner wet region of fish and water will évaporâtes as it recaches the surface (négligeable résistance to mass Transfer). These results are in a good agreement with (Ayoub, 2006) in her study of solar drying of tomato slices.

Figure 4. Shows the Variation of Moisture Content with Drying Time for the Three Days of the Drying

As shown in Table 5. Drying of fish flakes starts with an average initial moisture content of 78.67% (w.b.) and ends with an average final moisture content of about 11.41% (w.b.). The total drying time of fish flakes through the three drying days is about 33 hours. These results are in agreement with (Jain, 2006) on his study of drying kinetics of fish.

Figure 5. Moisture Content of Open Sun and Close Solar Drying of Fish Flakes with Time

Table 5. Average Results of Moisture Content (mc) % and Weight Losses in Grams for Representative Samples of Fish Flakes Dried with Solar Drier

Trial No.	Initial wt.(g)	Dried fish solar drying wt. (g)	Dried fish dry matter Wt.(g)	Initial mc% (w.b.)	Initial mc % (d.b)	Final mc% (w.b.)	Final mc% (d.b.)	Drying time (h)
1	30	9.33	6.20	79.33	383.87	10.43	50.48	33
2	30	9.99	6.30	79.00	376.19	12.30	58.57	33
3	30	10.15	6.70	77.67	347.76	11.50	51.49	33
average	30	9.82	6.40	78.67	369.27	11.41	53.51	33

Fig 5. Shows the variation of moisture content of fish flakes between natural open sun drying and natural convective solar drying. The decrease in moisture content of solar drying is greater than of the sun drying throughout the three drying days. This might be attributed to the increase in temperature and decreases in relative humidity of the drying air inside solar collector so that drying is greater than of the sun drying throughout the three drying days. Similar results have been reported by (Berinyuy, 2004) on study of solar tunnel for natural convective drying of vegetables and (Sacilik, 2006) on the study of organic tomato.

Conclusion

Solar dryer increasing the temperatures of the drying air of fish considerably and decreasing its relative humidity. This result in lowering the final moisture content of fish dried with solar dryer when comparing to the same fish drying with an open-direct sun.

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